

Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Oxalic Acid and its Homologues, Induced by Potassium Permanganate

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A comparative study of reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid and its homologues in presence of potassium permanganate used as an inductor has been made. The rate of reduction by oxalic acid has been found to be greater than that by malonic acid. The other higher homologues do not reduce mercuric chloride.

The present investigations include a comparative study of the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid and its homologues in presence of potassium permanganate, used as an inductor.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure adopted for studying the kinetics of reduction of mercuric chloride was the same as reported earlier¹.

DISCUSSION

The rate of reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid is greater than that by

FIG. 1

1—Oxalic acid. 2—Malonic acid.
Acid = 0.1M. $HgCl_2 = KMnO_4 = 0.01M$. Temp. = 20°.

malonic acid (Fig. 1). Succinic acid and other higher homologues do not reduce mercuric chloride. From this it is inferred that an increase in $-CH_2$ group in the acid molecule reduces the reducing power of these carboxylic acids.

The $x-t$ curves (Fig. 1) for the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid and malonic acid in presence of $KMnO_4$, used as an inductor, are of similar nature, suggesting that the same mechanism governs both the reactions. Both the reactions consist of three zones, viz., (1) period of induction, (2) auto-catalysis, and (3) autoinhibition accompanied by a normal reaction.

The oxalic acid complex $K_3Mn(C_2O_4)_3$ formed during the

1. Bansal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 1001; 1964, 41, 790; 1965, 42, 232, 235.

reaction is more stable than the malonic acid complex², $K_3Mn(C_3H_2O_4)_3$; hence it is inferred that the period of induction with oxalic acid should be greater than that with malonic acid and this fact is supported by our observations (Fig. 1). The period of induction has been described as the time required for formation of an unstable acid complex and its subsequent decomposition¹.

Fig. 1 also shows that the amount of mercuric chloride reduced in a certain time is much greater in the case of oxalic acid than in malonic acid, evidently due to the rate of formation of CO_2^- radicals which are responsible for the reduction of mercuric ions to mercurous state ($Hg^{2+} + CO_2^- \rightarrow Hg^+ + CO_2^{\cdot}$) being faster in the case of oxalic acid, as $C_2O_4^{2-}$ ions, which interact with Mn^{3+} ions to produce CO_2^- radicals ($Mn^{3+} + C_2O_4^{2-} \rightarrow CO_2 + CO_2^- + Mn^{2+}$), are already present in the reaction mixture. In the case of malonic acid, these $C_2O_4^{2-}$ ions are, however, obtained after different oxidation stages of the acid¹, i.e., malonic acid \rightarrow tartronic acid \rightarrow glyoxalic acid \rightarrow oxalic acid $\rightarrow C_2O_4^{2-}$.

The autocatalysis and autoinhibition start earlier in the case of malonic acid than in oxalic acid (Fig 1). This is due to the fact that the oxalic acid complex, being more stable than the malonic acid complex, helps the formation of the CO_2^- radicals for a longer period and thereby the chains are elongated and autoinhibition is reached later.

TABLE I

*Effect of sodium acetate.*Acid = 0.1M. $HgCl_2 = KMnO_4 = 0.01M$. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of NaAc.	Oxalic acid.		Malonic acid.	
	pH.	*KIO ₃ .	pH.	*KIO ₃ .
—	1.50	7.3 ml	2.20	4.3 ml
0.01M	1.60	7.7	2.30	4.6
0.02	1.70	8.4	2.42	4.9*
0.04	2.02	9.2	3.40	4.8
0.10	3.63	9.7	3.73	2.2
0.20	4.32	9.6	4.46	1.5
0.30	4.60	9.5	4.68	1.4
0.40	4.80	9.3
0.50	4.92	7.0

*Used in 60 min.

Table I shows that sodium acetate accelerates the rate of reduction of mercuric chloride up to a certain concentration, beyond which it retards the reaction. It also appears from Table I that at low pH (1.5–3.63 in the case of oxalic acid and 2.2–2.42 in the case of malonic acid), sodium acetate exerts the kinetic salt effect, but at higher pH (above 4.32 for oxalic acid and above 3.4 for malonic acid), it retards the reaction. It is due to the fact that at higher pH the oxalic acid and malonic acid complexes acquire greater stability,

2. Cartledge *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 2061, 2065; 1940, **62**, 3057.3. Jordon and Smith, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, p. 246.

thereby furnishing less oxalate and malonate ions which ultimately produce CO_2^- radicals¹, responsible for reduction of mercuric chloride. This fact is also confirmed by the work of Cartledge *et al.*² who have reported that these complexes are most stable at $\text{pH} \approx 5$.

Table II shows that the reduction of mercuric chloride increases with an increase in the concentration of the organic acid up to a certain limit, beyond which it begins to decrease. This is attributed to the fact that the reactions:

move faster in the forward direction at low concentrations of oxalate and malonate ions but at high concentrations the backward reaction overweighs the forward reaction, thereby retarding the decomposition of the complex which ultimately is responsible for the reduction.

TABLE II
Effect of the initial concentration of the acid.

Conc. of acid.	Mercurous chloride formed in 60 min.	
	With oxalic acid at 20°.	With malonic acid at 25°.
0.05 M	$1.35 \times 10^{-4} M$	$1.75 \times 10^{-4} M$
0.10	2.35	2.40
0.20	2.57	3.00
0.30	2.50	3.25
0.40	2.40	3.45
0.50	2.28	3.60
0.60	..	3.45
0.70	..	3.35

Table III shows that CO_2 catalyses both the reactions. This is due to the formation of more CO_2^- radicals as an interaction of CO_2 molecules with an electron from the acid ($\text{CO}_2 + e^- \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^-$)³. It also shows that oxygen has a retarding influence on the reduction of mercuric chloride in the case of oxalic acid; but in the case of malonic acid it has an accelerating influence. The retarding effect of oxygen in case of oxalic acid is due to removal of CO_2^- radicals at a faster rate by the chain-breaking step:

In the case of malonic acid, the accelerating effect is, however, due to the fact that the rate of oxidation of glyoxalic acid is highly enhanced as compared to the rate of removal of CO_2^- radicals¹.

TABLE III
Effect of oxygen and carbon dioxide.
Acid = 0.1M. $\text{HgCl}_2 = \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.01M$.

Gas.	Volume of KIO_3 used.	
	Oxalic acid.	Malonic acid.
Nil	4.6 ml	4.2 ml
O_2	1.2	5.0
CO_2	5.0	4.6

Thanks are due to Dr. A. K. Bhattacharya, Prof. of Chemistry, University of Jammu and Kashmir, and to Dr. L. K. Saxena, Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra, for their keen interest during the course of these investigations. The authors are also thankful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, Agra College, for providing necessary facilities and to the Government of India for awarding a research scholarship to one of them (P.C.M.).

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Received April 28, 1965.